

The Role of Informal Labour in Vietnam's Economic Growth

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Abstract

Background: Informal labour is an inseparable part of the economy, particularly in developing countries such as Vietnam. This sector comprises a significant portion of the workforce and plays a crucial role in job creation, income generation, and maintaining social stability. Despite its perceived inefficiencies, the informal sector makes a significant contribution to sustaining aggregate demand and economic resilience, particularly during economic downturns.

Objective: This article analyses the impact of informal labour on Vietnam's economic growth using empirical data.

Methodology: The study employs panel data collected by province from the General Statistics Office of Vietnam for the period 2018–2022. It utilises the System Generalised Method of Moments (S-GMM) to address endogeneity and assess the influence of informal labour, alongside capital, income, and demographic variables, on regional economic growth (GRDP).

Results: The findings indicate that informal labour has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth in Vietnam. In particular, increases in average income and informal employment are closely associated with higher GRDP. The study also reveals that population growth may have adverse effects if not accompanied by improvements in education and infrastructure.

Conclusion: The empirical evidence confirms the informal labour sector's supportive, statistically significant role in driving economic growth in Vietnam. The strong positive association between increases in average income and informal employment with Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) highlights the sector's crucial function in stabilising labour markets and sustaining domestic consumption.

Unique Contribution: This study provides robust empirical evidence on the role of informal labour in economic growth using the S-GMM methodology. It highlights the dynamic interaction between informal employment and macro-economic performance, reinforcing the argument that informal sectors, while often undervalued, are vital to the functioning and resilience of developing

economies like Vietnam.

Key Recommendation: Government authorities should formally recognise the informal sector in national development strategies. Specific policy measures—such as flexible social-protection schemes, access to microcredit, vocational training, and representation in policymaking—need to be adopted to strengthen productivity, resilience, and the integration of informal labour into the formal economy.

Keywords: Social security; informal labour; economic growth; human resources

Introduction

The informal economy is a common reality and has become a key concern in countries' economic and social development policies (Elbahnasawy, 2021; Estevao et al., 2022). The informal sector is a complex and often misunderstood component of modern economies, particularly in the developing world. It is characterised by small-scale, unregulated, and often precarious employment that operates outside formal legal and social protection frameworks (Charmes, 2022). Despite these limitations, it represents a significant portion of the total workforce in many countries, playing a vital role in job creation and income generation for a large segment of the population. In Vietnam, with a rapidly growing economy and an expanding urban population, the informal labour force has become a major driver of economic activity, providing livelihoods to millions who are not absorbed into the formal sector. According to the National Statistics Office of Vietnam, in 2023, the informal labour force outside the agricultural sector accounted for about 54.5% of the total working population. Of these, only about 8% participated in compulsory or voluntary social insurance, indicating that the majority of workers remain outside the social safety net. These limitations make them the most vulnerable group to economic shocks, as was clearly demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic when millions of informal workers lost their jobs without regular support or unemployment insurance (General Statistics Office of Vietnam, 2022).

The role of informal labour in economic development has been a subject of extensive debate. Early views, often associated with the dual-economy model by Mazumdar (1981), considered the informal sector as a "reserve army" of underemployed labour waiting to transition to the formal sector. Similarly, the work of Doeringer and Piore (1971) described the informal sector as a flexible buffer zone, absorbing excess labour that the formal sector cannot accommodate.

However, more recent perspectives challenge this view, suggesting that the informal sector is a dynamic and essential part of the economy. Chen (2004) argues that the informal sector is not simply a survival mechanism but also complements the formal sector by providing low-cost goods and services and promoting value chains. Furthermore, Maloney (2004) posits that informal employment is often a voluntary choice for entrepreneurs and workers seeking greater flexibility and autonomy, rather than a last resort. This entrepreneurial spirit, a key driver of growth according to Schumpeter (1934), is often found in the informal sector. A study by Gindling and Newhouse (2014) on self-employment in developing countries supports this idea, highlighting its role in fostering livelihoods and economic resilience.

In the context of dynamic economic models, the informal sector's contribution is often linked to its ability to maintain consumption and domestic demand, which are crucial for sustained growth

(Fields, 2005). The challenge, therefore, is not to eliminate the informal sector but to find integrated approaches that gradually formalise it and improve its efficiency, thereby maximising its potential contribution to sustainable economic growth (Nahid et al., 2024).

Objective

The purpose of this study is to provide a contemporary analysis of the impact of informal labour on Vietnam's economic growth, using recent data and an advanced econometric methodology. While prior research has examined the informal sector's role in other contexts, a gap remains in understanding its specific contribution and dynamics within Vietnam's unique economic environment. This article aims to fill that gap by empirically examining the relationship between informal employment and Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP), and by providing targeted policy recommendations to integrate better and support this vital segment of the economy.

Methodology

The topic uses the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) proposed by Lars Peter Hansen in 1982. The use of the GMM model will allow us to overcome the shortcomings of the model, such as autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, and endogeneity, ensuring that the estimation results are unbiased, stable, and most effective. The GMM method has two alternative estimation forms: difference GMM estimation (D-GMM) and system GMM estimation (S-GMM). Accordingly, the D-GMM estimation of Arellano and Bond (1995) is suitable when the sample size is small; otherwise, the S-GMM estimation of Arellano and Bover (1995), Blundell and Bond (1998) should be chosen.

For the GMM model's estimation results, the Arellano-Bond and Hansen tests are required. GMM estimation assumes that the residuals are uncorrelated with their own lagged values. Therefore, we need to test for autocorrelation in the error component using the Arellano-Bond test (1991). Accordingly, GMM estimation requires the presence of first-order autocorrelation - AR(1) and no second-order autocorrelation - AR(2) of the residuals.

Hypothesis H_0 : There is no first-order or second-order autocorrelation of the residuals. Therefore, we need to reject the hypothesis H_0 in the AR(1) test, but want to accept H_0 in the AR(2) test.

The Sargan/Hansen test is used to determine the appropriateness of the instrumental variables in the GMM model. This is an over-identifying restriction test of the model, with the hypothesis H_0 : the instrumental variables are exogenous, that is, uncorrelated with the model error. Accordingly, we want to accept the hypothesis H_0 with the theoretical Prob value greater than 0.05 or 0.1.

This study uses Stata 17 software with the command "xtabond2" to estimate the impact model of informal labour on Vietnam's economic growth according to S-GMM estimation.

Research model

Based on the Cobb–Douglas production function, if we ignore the technology factor (A), the general production function is written as follows:

$$Y = f(K, L) \quad (1)$$

Where Y is output level, K is capital, and L is labour.

In addition, we add some other control variables, which are the lagged variable of output $Y(-1)$, population (DS) and average income of labour (TN). Thus, equation (1) can be rewritten as follows:

$$Y = f(Y(-1), K, L, DS, TN) \quad (2)$$

Take the natural logarithm of both sides of equation 2 and replace the symbol Y with GRDP, we have:

$$\text{LN GRDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LN GRDP}(-1) + \beta_2 \text{LN K} + \beta_3 \text{LN L} + \beta_4 \text{LN DS} + \beta_5 \text{LN TN} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

In there:

- *GRDP*: is the gross regional domestic product of Vietnam, unit is million VND.
- *GRDP (-1)*: Is the past value (previous period) of the gross regional domestic product of Vietnam. The past value of GRDP is assumed to have a positive impact on the current GRDP.
- *Capital (K)*: Due to the lack of available data on capital, the author uses the representative indicator of total production and business capital of enterprises by locality in Vietnam. Capital is a resource factor of the economy, so K is assumed to have a positive impact on GRDP.
- *Labour (L)*: The labour used in the study is the informal labour force working in Vietnam by locality. Similar to capital, the labour variable L is also assumed to have a positive impact on GRDP.
- *Population (DS)*: is the total population of Vietnam by locality. Population affects the economy in the following ways:
 - + Population growth means a more abundant labour force, contributing to boosting production.
 - + Large population creates high demand for goods and services, promoting consumption.
 - + A large population, especially when well educated, can generate many innovative ideas and new technologies, helping the economy grow.
 Thus, the population has a positive impact on GRDP.
- *Income (TN)*: is the average income of labourers in each locality of Vietnam, adjusted to the original price in 2010. When income increases, people will increase spending and therefore aggregate demand will increase. Therefore, TN is assumed to have a positive impact on GRDP.
- ε_t is the residual, representing the impact of other factors not mentioned in the model.
- β_i are coefficients.

Table 1. Expected signs of variables in the model

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Expectation Sign
GRDP (-1)		+
Capital (K)		+
Labour (L)	GRDP	+
Population (DS)		+
Income (TN)		+

Data used in the model

The project uses annual data collected from the Vietnam General Statistics Office (NSO). The data used in the analysis were collected by locality in Vietnam between 2018 and 2022 (as of 2023, the NSO has not updated some indicators).

Descriptive statistical analysis and correlation matrix

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of research variables

Variable	Number of observations (N)	Mean	Standard Deviation (Std. Dev.)	Minimum value (Min)	Maximum value (Max)
GRDP	315	128,349.90	207,752.40	10,970.46	1,462,111.00
K	315	560,624.2	1,703,825	10,648	11,800,000
L	315	579.5341	387,1459	107,7505	2,533.12
TN	315	5,023.25	1,384,158	2,059.8	9.103
DS	315	1,547,379	1,444,905	312	9,389.72

Source: Author's calculation on STATA software

Table 2 presents the statistical results for the model variables. Accordingly, the average value of gross regional domestic product (GRDP) is 128,349.9 million VND. The locality with the largest gross regional domestic product is Ho Chi Minh City, with 1,462,111 million VND in 2022, and the lowest is Bac Kan province, with only 10,970.46 million VND in 2018. The average capital value (K) is 560,624.2 billion VND, with a maximum of 11,800,000 billion VND and a minimum of 10,648 billion VND. In which the most significant capital value belongs to Hanoi city in 2022, the smallest belongs to Bac Kan province in 2018. The number of informal workers (L) has an average value of 579.5 thousand people, the most considerable value is 2,533.12 thousand people in Hanoi city in 2018, and the smallest value is 107.75 thousand people in Cao Bang province in 2021. The average income of workers by locality (TN) is 5,023.25 thousand VND; the largest is 9,103 thousand VND, and the smallest is 2,059.8 thousand VND. Ho Chi Minh City is the locality with the highest average income of workers in 2022, while Cao Bang is the locality with the lowest average income of workers in 2018. The population of the localities (DS) is 1,547,379 on average. In which Ho Chi Minh City has the largest population of 9,389,72 thousand people in 2022, and Bac Kan province has the least population of 312 thousand people in 2018.

Table 3. Pearson correlation matrix

Variable	lnGRDP	lnK	lnL	lnTN	lnDS
LNGRD	1				
LNK	0.9489 (0.0000)	1			
LNL	0.6874 (0.0000)	0.5938 (0.0000)	1		
LTN	0.7899 (0.0000)	0.7568 (0.0000)	0.3352 (0.0000)	1	
LNDS	0.8871 (0.0000)	0.8185 (0.0000)	0.9087 (0.0000)	0.6031 (0.0000)	1

Source: Author's calculation on STATA software

Note:

- The values in the cell corresponding to each pair of variables are the correlation coefficients.
- The values in the second row below each pair are the corresponding p-value (statistical significance level).
- The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1. The further the coefficient is from 0, the stronger the correlation.

The Pearson correlation matrix shown in Table 3 reflects the two-way relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables in the research model. Accordingly, the larger the correlation coefficient, the closer the relationship between the variables. Based on the correlation matrix, it shows that the dependent variable has a relatively close relationship with the independent variables. However, this is a single two-way relationship between pairs of variables. To assess the impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable in the binding relationship between all variables, in the following section we will analyze the regression according to the research model identified above.

Estimation results

Table 4. S-GMM model estimation results

Dependent variable: LNGRDP

Independent variable	Coefficient	Standard error	P-Value
LNGRDP(-1)	0.7514	0.0584	0.000
LNK	0.0686	0.0296	0.020
LNL	0.1610	0.0244	0.000

LTN	0.4725	0.0409	0.000
LNDS	-0.0614	0.0344	0.074
Constant term	-2.5493	0.2460	0.000

Arellano-Bond test for AR(1) in first differences: $z = -2,69$ $Pr > z = 0.007$

Arellano-Bond test for AR(2) in first differences: $z = -0,74$ $Pr > z = 0.459$

Sargan test of overid, restrictions: $\chi^2(11) = 32,76$ $Prob > \chi^2 = 0.001$

(Not robust, but not weakened by many instruments)

Hansen test of overid, restrictions: $\chi^2(11) = 16,61$ $Prob > \chi^2 = 0.120$

(Robust, but weakened by many instruments)

Source: Author's calculation on STATA software

The results of estimating the model to study the impact of informal labour on Vietnam's economic growth are shown in Table 4. In which, the independent variables are identified as endogenous variables, namely LNDRDP(-1) and LNTN, because the output of the economy and labour income are the results of economic activities, so they are affected by input variables in the model such as capital, labour, population, etc. The remaining independent variables are identified as exogenous in the model.

For the autocorrelation test according to Arellano and Bond (1991), the results show that the hypothesis H_0 is rejected in the AR(1) test but the AR(2) test accepts the hypothesis H_0 . This means that the research model has first-order autocorrelation but no second-order autocorrelation.

The Hansen test shows that the instruments used in the model are appropriate ($p = 0.120$), although the Sargan test rejects the null hypothesis H_0 ($p = 0.001$). The Hansen test is a more robust test and should be preferred.

From the estimation results, the research model on the impact of informal labour on Vietnam's economic growth is determined to have the following form:

$$LNDRDP = -2,55 + 0,75LNDRDP(-1) + 0,069LNK + 0,161LNL + 0,47LNTN - 0,06LNDS + u$$

Discussion

The empirical findings from our S-GMM model provide strong evidence that informal labour is a significant and positive contributor to Vietnam's economic growth. The positive and statistically significant coefficient for informal labour (LNL) at 0.1610 directly supports the hypothesis that this sector, while often undervalued, is a vital economic engine.

This result aligns with recent literature that views the informal sector as more than just a survival mechanism. It suggests that, in the context of Vietnam's developing economy, the informal sector's role in creating employment and providing low-cost goods and services outweighs its perceived inefficiencies. This is consistent with the findings of Maloney (2004) and Gindling & Newhouse (2014), who highlight the entrepreneurial and job-creation aspects of informal work.

A particularly noteworthy finding is the negative coefficient for the population variable (LNDS). This deviates from the initial hypothesis that population growth would positively impact GRDP. A plausible explanation for this result is that in the study period, population growth may have outpaced the economy's capacity to absorb it productively, leading to increased pressure on existing infrastructure, social services, and the formal labour market. This highlights a crucial policy challenge: ensuring that population growth is accompanied by investments in education, skills training, and infrastructure to transform demographic expansion into a genuine economic asset. This has been shown in previous studies, emphasizing the importance of education, health, and institutional capacity in converting demographic trends into productive assets (Loayza, 1996; Medina & Schneider, 2018).

The strong positive coefficient of the lagged GRDP variable (LNGRDP(-1)) at 0.7514 confirms the dynamic nature of economic growth, where past performance is a powerful predictor of current and future growth. This suggests that positive momentum in economic policy and development has a long-lasting effect. Moreover, the strong effect of average income on GRDP is consistent with Keynesian economic theory, where increased income leads to higher consumption and thus economic expansion.

Conclusion and policy implications

This study analyzed the role of informal labour in Vietnam's economic growth during the period 2018–2022, showing that informal labour has a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth, in addition to traditional factors such as capital, income and GRDP in the past. This reflects that, although the informal sector is often considered inefficient and unsustainable, it is making a substantial contribution to growth through job creation, provision of low-cost goods and services and maintaining livelihoods for the majority of the population.

From the above findings, the study proposes some policy implications as follows:

First, the state needs to officially recognize the role of the informal sector in the socio-economic development strategy. This is not only symbolic but also creates a foundation for building appropriate support and management policies, instead of letting this sector exist in a legal “gray zone”.

Second, design policies to protect and support informal workers flexibly, suitable to their unstable and informal characteristics, such as voluntary social insurance policies, micro-credit incentives, and access to small-scale production infrastructure.

Third, there is a need for programmes to build production capacity, strengthen vocational skills, and improve value chain connectivity to enhance competitiveness and operational efficiency in the informal sector.

Fourth, strengthen dialogue mechanisms and represent the voice of the informal sector in the policy-making process. The government can support the formation of professional organisations, cooperatives or community networks to represent the specific interests and needs of this group of workers.

The above policy implications will improve the effectiveness of labour market management while maximising the potential contribution of the informal sector to Vietnam's sustainable economic growth and development in the near future.

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